

Accelerating Apache Spark Performance in Clean Rooms

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Contents

1	Accelerating Apache Spark Performance in Clean Rooms	3
1.1	Abstract	3
1.2	Introduction	3
1.2.1	Key findings	4
1.3	Motivation: Why Accelerate Spark in the Clean Room	4
1.4	Apache Spark Performance Challenges	5
1.4.1	The columnar era	5
1.5	Solution: Native Columnar Execution with Comet	6
1.5.1	Key features	6
1.5.2	How Comet integrates with Spark	7
1.6	Architecture and Performance Comparison	7
1.7	Production Benchmark Results	9
1.7.1	Test configuration	9
1.7.2	Workload coverage	9
1.7.3	Results summary	9
1.8	Production Deployment	9
1.8.1	Recommended configuration	10
1.8.2	Deployment phases	10
1.8.3	Partition tuning strategy	10
1.8.4	The memory paradox	10
1.8.5	Shuffle volume fallback	11
1.9	Performance Impact and Business Outcomes	11
1.10	References	11
1.11	Further Reading	11

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This technical report describes how LiveRamp accelerated Apache Spark execution in production clean room environments by adopting DataFusion Comet, a native columnar Spark accelerator built on Apache DataFusion and Apache Arrow. Clean room workloads process multi-terabyte, multi-party datasets under strict SLAs and cost constraints. Traditional JVM row-oriented Spark execution introduces overhead from garbage collection, serialization, and row-to-column conversions that limit performance on analytical queries. Comet provides a drop-in execution layer that preserves Spark's Catalyst optimizer and PySpark/Scala APIs while offloading supported operators to a Rust-native backend. We present architecture comparisons, production benchmark results across measurement and attribution pipelines, deployment configuration, operational lessons (partition tuning, memory management, shuffle fallback), and measured runtime improvements of up to 49.5% on representative production queries running Apache Spark 3.5.5 and Comet 0.11.0 on Kubernetes across AWS, Azure, and GCP.

1 Accelerating Apache Spark Performance in Clean Rooms

1.1 Abstract

This technical report describes how LiveRamp accelerated Apache Spark execution in production clean room environments by adopting DataFusion Comet, a native columnar Spark accelerator built on Apache DataFusion and Apache Arrow. Clean room workloads process multi-terabyte, multi-party datasets under strict SLAs and cost constraints. Traditional JVM row-oriented Spark execution introduces overhead from garbage collection, serialization, and row-to-column conversions that limit performance on analytical queries. Comet provides a drop-in execution layer that preserves Spark’s Catalyst optimizer and PySpark/Scala APIs while offloading supported operators to a Rust-native backend.

We present architecture comparisons, production benchmark results across measurement and attribution pipelines, deployment configuration, operational lessons (partition tuning, memory management, shuffle fallback), and measured runtime improvements of up to 49.5% on representative production queries.

Reference stack

Component	Version
Apache Spark	3.5.5
DataFusion Comet	0.11.0
Orchestration	Spark on Kubernetes (EKS, GKE, AKS)
Data formats	Apache Parquet (primary)

1.2 Introduction

The LiveRamp Clean Room is a secure, cloud-agnostic environment that enables data collaboration between brands, agencies, publishers, retail media networks, and platforms. It allows participants to join, analyze, and activate data across partners while supporting strict data governance and usage controls. This capability is powered by a cloud-native data plane architecture that runs entirely within the client’s chosen cloud environment (AWS, Azure, or GCP), supporting data localization and security across multiple zones for high availability.

Apache Spark serves as the underlying processing engine for the clean room, orchestrated by Kubernetes to dynamically scale compute resources based on workload demand. This architecture allows customers to run complex, large-scale analytics across multi-party datasets while minimizing data movement outside their own cloud environment.

As clean room workloads continue to grow in size and complexity, the performance of this processing layer becomes critical. Customers depend on the LiveRamp Clean Room to deliver daily insights across terabytes of partner data, often under strict SLAs and cost constraints. Queries frequently involve large joins, heavy aggregations, and scans across columnar datasets.

Even small inefficiencies in execution can translate into longer runtimes, higher infrastructure usage, and delayed results.

To support these increasing demands while maintaining the same secure and cloud-agnostic architecture, we needed to improve the performance and efficiency of Spark without requiring changes to existing customer workloads.

1.2.1 Key findings

- Clean room performance is critical at scale. As workloads grow to multi-terabyte datasets, even small inefficiencies in Spark execution can impact runtime, cost, and SLA reliability.
- Row-based execution creates bottlenecks for modern analytics. Traditional Spark introduces overhead through JVM processing, memory management, and row-to-column conversions—limiting efficiency for columnar data workloads.
- Columnar, native execution significantly improves performance. By leveraging DataFusion Comet with Apache Arrow, LiveRamp enables faster scans, joins, and aggregations while reducing memory usage and serialization overhead.
- Performance gains come without code changes. Comet acts as a drop-in Spark accelerator, allowing existing PySpark and Scala workloads to run unchanged while benefiting from native execution improvements.
- Faster queries translate directly to business impact. Improved performance reduces infrastructure costs, accelerates insights, and enables more scalable, reliable data collaboration in the LiveRamp Clean Room.

1.3 Motivation: Why Accelerate Spark in the Clean Room

Several factors drove the need to improve Spark execution performance across our production clean room environments.

Scale challenge. Processing terabytes of cross-media data from multiple partners—including publishers, DSPs, and retail media networks—in a unified view requires significant computational power. Clean room queries often operate on multi-terabyte datasets spread across many partitions and storage systems.

Speed requirements. Customers rely on clean rooms for daily reporting, measurement, and attribution workflows. Insights must be delivered quickly and predictably, but traditional Spark execution, while reliable, cannot always meet the aggressive runtime targets required for production workloads.

Cost efficiency. Clean room workloads run continuously across hundreds of environments. Even modest performance improvements can reduce total cluster runtime, lowering infrastructure costs while allowing more workloads to run on the same hardware.

Data complexity. Clean room queries commonly include:

- Multi-party joins across disparate datasets
- Complex de-duplication logic for accurate reach measurement
- Heavy aggregations for attribution and performance analysis

- Large-scale scans of Parquet and other columnar formats

These patterns are particularly sensitive to memory usage, shuffle performance, and CPU efficiency.

Resource optimization. Improving CPU utilization and memory efficiency allows us to support more customers on the same infrastructure while maintaining predictable performance for business-critical analytics.

To address these challenges, LiveRamp introduced DataFusion Comet as a native execution accelerator for Spark. By enabling columnar, native execution without requiring application changes, we were able to improve performance while preserving the reliability and compatibility of our existing clean room platform.

1.4 Apache Spark Performance Challenges

Modern Apache Spark is a highly flexible distributed engine capable of processing terabytes of data through SQL or its DataFrame API. Its maturity, extensive connectivity, numerous integrations, and robust design make it one of the most versatile distributed engines available—handling everything from distributed machine learning and graph processing to SQL workloads in data warehouses and lakehouses.

However, this versatility comes at a cost. Due to its Resilient Distributed Dataset (RDD) legacy, Spark primarily uses row-oriented data representation in memory. Despite improvements from Project Tungsten’s code generation and vectorized readers, operators still incur significant overhead from Java object creation, garbage collection, and row-to-column conversions.

These costs become especially visible in analytical workloads that dominate clean room processing, including large Parquet scans, wide joins, and memory-intensive aggregations. In these scenarios, Spark can spend significant time managing objects and memory rather than performing actual computation, leading to slower queries and inefficient CPU utilization compared to engines designed for columnar execution.

1.4.1 The columnar era

Row-oriented execution works well for certain types of data, particularly unstructured or semi-structured formats such as text, CSV, or XML. However, modern data platforms, including clean rooms, are built around columnar storage formats such as Apache Parquet, Apache ORC, and table frameworks like Delta Lake, Iceberg, and Hudi.

In these environments, row-based execution introduces unnecessary overhead. Data stored in columnar form must often be converted into rows before operators can process it, and then converted back into columns for output. Even with efficient implementations, these conversions add CPU cost and increase memory pressure.

Clean room workloads are especially sensitive to this overhead because they frequently scan large columnar datasets, perform wide joins, and aggregate across many columns. A more efficient

approach is to keep data in columnar format throughout execution and operate directly on contiguous memory buffers.

This shift toward columnar processing motivated us to explore native execution engines that could integrate with Spark while avoiding the overhead of row-based execution.

1.5 Solution: Native Columnar Execution with Comet

To improve performance without changing the programming model used by our customers, we looked for a way to keep Spark’s optimizer and APIs while replacing the row-oriented execution layer with a native, columnar engine.

DataFusion Comet provides exactly this capability. Comet is a Spark accelerator built on top of the Apache DataFusion query engine, which is written in Rust and uses Apache Arrow as its in-memory format. This allows execution to occur in native code using columnar data structures, avoiding JVM overhead while maintaining compatibility with existing Spark applications.

With Comet, Spark’s Catalyst optimizer still produces the execution plan, but supported operators are executed by the native backend. Unsupported operators automatically fall back to the standard Spark engine to help maintain correctness and reliability.

This approach allows users to continue using the same PySpark and Scala APIs while benefiting from:

- SIMD-optimized columnar execution
- Reduced serialization overhead
- More efficient memory usage
- Faster scans and joins on columnar data

Most importantly, these improvements require no changes to existing customer workloads.

1.5.1 Key features

Feature	Description
Plan conversion	Converts Spark’s physical execution plan to a native backend plan
Fallback processing	Detects unsupported features and falls back to the Spark JVM engine
Memory management	Uses Spark’s memory manager while executing operators in native code
Columnar shuffle	Uses Arrow-based shuffle for more efficient data exchange
Shim layer	Supports multiple versions of Spark for seamless integration

1.5.2 How Comet integrates with Spark

Comet is a native Spark query execution plugin that integrates with Spark's plugin framework and extensions API. The driver-based plugin updates Spark configuration with additional executor memory settings. Physical plan optimization rules (CometScanRule and CometExecRule) determine which operations can be accelerated through native execution.

Comet works through `org.apache.spark.api.plugin.SparkPlugin`:

```
class CometPlugin extends SparkPlugin with Logging {  
  override def driverPlugin(): DriverPlugin = new CometDriverPlugin  
  override def executorPlugin(): ExecutorPlugin = null  
}
```

This design allows Comet to accelerate queries transparently while preserving the behavior of existing applications.

1.6 Architecture and Performance Comparison

Below is a side-by-side comparison of traditional Apache Spark and Apache Spark with Comet across execution model, memory management, data format handling, and operational characteristics.

Category	Apache Spark	DataFusion + Comet	Impact
Execution model	JVM-based, distributed; uses Spark SQL Catalyst and Tungsten	Rust-based, vectorized, Arrow-native execution	Comet avoids JVM overhead and uses highly efficient Rust
Memory management	JVM heap and off-heap; requires garbage collection; tuned via executor memory, overhead, and shuffle buffers	Fully native memory using Rust/Arrow; no garbage collection; direct columnar memory layout	Comet uses less memory for same workloads and avoids GC pauses
Data format	Converts many inputs to Spark's internal row-based Tungsten format unless using columnar operators	Uses Apache Arrow columnar format end-to-end	Less serialization leads to lower memory footprint and faster compute
Parquet reading	Row-wise decoding in many cases; vectorization exists but limited functions work columnar	Native Rust Parquet reader with full vectorization	Comet/DataFusion often 2-5x faster on scan-heavy workloads
Memory during joins	Can be heavy due to shuffle, sort, and JVM overhead; spills to disk when memory insufficient	Arrow-native hash tables and sort algorithms; more efficient memory use	Comet joins generally use less memory and spill later
Shuffle	Expensive due to serialization into JVM objects; shuffle files often large	Arrow IPC batches; faster shuffle and smaller spill files	Lower disk usage and faster shuffle steps
UDF execution	JVM UDFs are slow, row-oriented	Rust UDFs are vectorized (but still maturing)	Comet wins for built-in functions; UDF feature set still growing
Predicate pushdown	Good pushdown, but sometimes limited by Catalyst and data source implementations	Minimal overhead; pushdown happens naturally via Arrow and Parquet reader	Better scan pruning and less I/O on Comet

1.7 Production Benchmark Results

We tested Comet against production clean room workloads across measurement, attribution, and data quality pipelines.

1.7.1 Test configuration

Component	Configuration
Cluster type	Spark on Kubernetes (EKS on AWS, GKE on GCP, AKS on Azure)
Spark version	3.5.5
Comet version	0.11.0
Executor configuration	spark.executor.memory=46g, spark.sql.shuffle.partitions between 600–10000, spark.executor.cores=4
Dataset scale	Multi-terabyte datasets of measurement, attribution, match, and quality assurance across the production clean room

1.7.2 Workload coverage

We tested Comet across production clean room queries spanning various industries and use cases:

- **Measurement solutions:** Multi-party matched impressions and reach analysis
- **Attribution queries:** Cross-platform attribution with large-scale joins
- **Data quality checks:** Retail media network data validation and conversion analysis
- **Mixed workloads:** Combination of ETL and analytical queries

1.7.3 Results summary

Performance category	Query count	Average improvement	Runtime reduction
Excellent (40%+)	8 queries	49.5% faster	42–75%
Good (20–40%)	14 queries	27% faster	20–30%
Moderate (0–20%)	8 queries	5.5% faster	0–20%

These improvements reduced cluster runtime, improved SLA consistency, and lowered total infrastructure usage across clean room environments.

1.8 Production Deployment

We deployed Comet in production through a carefully structured approach.

1.8.1 Recommended configuration

```
spark.comet.enabled = true
spark.comet.exec.enabled = true
spark.comet.expression.allowIncompatible = false
spark.comet.exec.shuffle.enabled = true
spark.comet.exec.shuffle.mode = auto
spark.comet.scan.enabled = false
spark.shuffle.manager =
org.apache.spark.sql.comet.execution.shuffle.CometShuffleManager
```

1.8.2 Deployment phases

1. **Centralized control:** Established Comet configurations at the organization level for streamlined management
2. **Pilot program:** Enabled Comet for a select group of clean room queries across multiple environments, testing both SQL and compute workloads while monitoring performance metrics
3. **Validation:** Verified that query results were consistent between standard Spark and Comet-accelerated execution
4. **Safety net:** Maintained the ability to quickly disable Comet organization-wide if issues emerged

We also introduced new instance types to support higher executor memory demands. The configured off-heap memory allocation became `spark.memory.offHeap.size=50g`.

1.8.3 Partition tuning strategy

Comet's columnar processing model requires careful consideration of partition sizing to avoid internal buffer limitations. The partition sizing must ensure individual vectors fit comfortably within internal limits, regardless of total available memory. More memory does not always mean better safety—proper partition sizing does.

```
spark.sql.shuffle.partitions = 600 to 10000 (based on workload complexity)
```

1.8.4 The memory paradox

Comet can spill to disk, but unlike standard Spark, it processes data in large columnar batches instead of row by row, which introduces a unique set of memory management challenges. In a traditional row-based Spark execution model, data is processed incrementally, allowing Spark to spill conservatively when memory pressure is detected and handle large partitions by gradually writing intermediate results to disk.

Comet's columnar execution model behaves differently. Because it operates on entire vector batches in memory, individual vectors must fit within internal buffer limits (typically around 2 GB for contiguous allocations). As a result, even when sufficient total memory appears to be available, Comet may not trigger a spill soon enough, leading to failures when a single vector exceeds the allowable size.

1.8.5 Shuffle volume fallback

Comet shuffle can show occasional instability under heavy workloads, especially when large shuffle volumes and memory pressure prevent sufficient disk spilling. In these cases, executor failures may occur, requiring a fallback to Spark's native shuffle to enable reliable job completion:

```
spark.comet.exec.shuffle.enabled = false  
spark.shuffle.manager = org.apache.spark.shuffle.sort.SortShuffleManager
```

1.9 Performance Impact and Business Outcomes

Adopting Comet significantly improved both performance and efficiency across LiveRamp Clean Room workloads without requiring any changes to existing Spark applications. By moving from JVM-managed memory to Arrow-based off-heap memory, we reduced garbage collection overhead, lowered heap pressure, and minimized unnecessary spill operations. Comet's native Rust execution engine, combined with SIMD-optimized columnar processing, delivers better CPU utilization, improved cache locality, and reduced serialization overhead compared to standard Spark execution.

These technical improvements translated directly into measurable business impact. Because Comet operates as a drop-in accelerator for Spark, our existing PySpark and Scala workloads run unchanged, allowing us to roll out performance gains safely across production environments. Automatic fallback to the standard Spark engine supported reliability while enabling us to take advantage of native execution wherever possible. Faster query runtimes reduced cluster runtime across hundreds of clean room environments, lowering infrastructure costs and improving overall resource utilization.

Customers now get insights faster and large multi-party workloads process more efficiently. LiveRamp is able to support more clean rooms on the same infrastructure while maintaining the performance and reliability required for business-critical analytics.

1.10 References

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1.11 Further Reading

- DataFusion Comet documentation

- [Apache Spark on Kubernetes](#)
- [Original LiveRamp blog post](#)